

THE ROLE OF MEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The article explores the importance and role of various media technologies in teaching the Russian language. The concepts of media education also consider educational, pedagogical, and creative approaches to the use of media opportunities in general.*

Keywords: *media technology, theory, industrial activity, integration, artistic aspect, aesthetic perception, information.*

РОЛЬ МЕДИАТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБУЧЕНИИ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *В статье исследуется значение и роль различных медиатехнологий в обучении русскому языку. Концепции медиаобразования рассматривают также образовательный, педагогический и творческий подходы к использованию возможностей медиа в целом.*

Ключевые слова: *медиатехнологии, теория, производственная деятельность, интеграция, художественный аспект, эстетическое восприятие, информация.*

In enhancing the information skills of future engineers for industrial activities in the Russian language, based on media technologies in higher technical educational institutions, it is an important factor in preparing them for technical professional activities and improving the methodology of teaching the Russian language.

Analyzing the aforementioned theories of media education in teaching the Russian language, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The "injection theory" of media education emphasizes the negative effects of mass media, including the adverse consequences of violence. In this context, media is seen as an "agent of cultural degradation," exemplified by comics, advertising, and unreliable media.

2. Many theoretical approaches align with the "development of professional-critical thinking" theory:

Media education helps students understand the fundamental laws and language of the artistic aspect of media information, aesthetic perception of artistic texts, and the ability to analyze them from a professional perspective when learning the Russian language.

As a result of integrating media education into teaching the Russian language, the following actions should occur: a professional-critical approach to knowledge acquired through media education, the ability to interpret information, accurately understand its intended

professional purpose, determine the goal of the information, establish one's position regarding the information, search for necessary information from various sources, systematize information based on specific criteria, and transform visual information into verbal sign systems and vice versa.

The effective use of information and communication technologies in developing students' professional knowledge, skills, and abilities in preparing them for professional activities by ensuring the integration of natural sciences and specialties in the higher education system when teaching the Russian language [1].

The analysis of foreign media education methodologies highlights the issue of the interaction between teachers and students.

Media education pursues two equal goals: the development of an integrative approach to media texts and the enhancement of students' communicative, professional, and creative abilities, i.e., the ability to receive, create, and transmit media texts. The analysis of foreign media education methodologies emphasizes the problem of the interaction between teachers and students [2].

Media communication skills (competence, awareness) involve the ability to perceive, create, and transmit messages through technical and semiotic systems, considering their limitations. It is based on a professional-critical approach and the ability to engage in media communications with others based on their professional knowledge.

The issue of the influence of mass communication on the formation of values and moral norms among students is particularly relevant: "It is no longer possible for a student to prepare for professional activity without forming a referential system of values and an integrative attitude toward messages transmitted through mass communication channels" [3].

In our view, students need to perform creative and practical tasks using various media forms when studying the Russian language. All this helps develop the ability to understand, evaluate, and interpret various media, as well as reveal students' communicative abilities.

Based on traditional didactic principles, the principles of media education are:

- 1) teaching and comprehensive development in the educational process;
- 2) scientific rigor and transparency in education;
- 3) the structure of teaching and the connection between theory and practice;
- 4) student activity;
- 5) clarity;
- 6) the transition from teaching to self-learning;
- 7) the connection between education and life;
- 8) the reliability of educational outcomes;

9) consideration of a positive emotional background and individual characteristics of learners while accounting for collective learning features;

10) the bifunctionality of aesthetic self-education, where aesthetic meaning clarifies ethical meaning.

Media education can be divided into the following main areas:

1) media education for future professionals in the world of press, radio, television, film, video, and the Internet—journalists, editors, directors, producers, actors, cameramen, etc.;

2) media education for future specialists in universities and institutes;

3) media education for school students and vocational schools, which can be integrated with traditional, professional, or specialized education;

4) media education in institutions of additional education and recreational facilities (cultural centers, extracurricular activities, aesthetic and artistic education centers, community clubs);

5) media education in industrial enterprises using press, television, radio, video, DVD, and Internet systems (where media criticism plays a significant role);

6) independent lifelong media education (theoretically, this can be done throughout a person's life).

Organizational forms include integrated and autonomous media education. Teaching methods in media education can be classified as follows:

- By sources of knowledge: verbal methods (lectures, storytelling, discussions, explanations); visual methods (illustration and demonstration of media texts); practical methods (performing various practical tasks based on media materials).

- By the level of cognitive activity: explanatory-illustrative methods (teachers providing specific information about media, which the audience receives and assimilates); problem-based methods (analyzing specific situations or media texts to develop critical thinking); research methods (organizing students' research activities). Practical and creative tasks hold a special place in lessons.

The selection of media information in English, its comprehensive perception, interpretation, and creative application form the basis for developing personal positions in media, while its independent and critical evaluation serves as the foundation for practical use in all production areas.

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